

Press release | 23 September 2024

South3E launches the S3E Charge Fast-Track Acceleration for Deep Tech startups in Southern Europe

Following the success of its two previous editions, the EU-funded initiative South3E is pleased to announce the launch of the third and final open call for the S3E Charge accelerator program.

In this new edition, the S3E Charge Fast-Track Acceleration, led by the experts of the Institute for Sustainable Development at EPLO, has been crafted to provide specialist support for deep tech startups in their growth stage in a fast-track manner. Throughout the 4-week duration of the program, up to 30 selected startups will have access to mentoring and training sessions hosted by leading industry experts.

The ultimate goal of the S3E Charge program is to help science-based entrepreneurs from Southern Europe develop a solid business plan to successfully access public and private funding, and in turn contribute towards building a robust deep tech innovation ecosystem in the region.

The application process for S3E Charge Fast-Track Acceleration opens on 23 September (12:00 CET) and closes on 11 October (17:00 CET). The program will run for 4 weeks, starting on 15 October and finishing on 8 November.

The startups interested in joining the program will need to [download the official S3E Application Guidelines](#) and [complete the application form on F6S](#). The South3E team also invites applicants to [join the S3E Charge Info Session](#) on 30 September at 12:00 CET.

The S3E Charge Fast-Track Acceleration welcomes applications from the following countries:

- **South European countries:** Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia and Spain.
- **Associated countries:** Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Kosovo and Turkey.

Since launching in 2022, S3E Charge has supported over 30 startups. This is the final chance to join the project leading the South European deep tech revolution!

More information about this program and the open call is available on the [S3E website](#).

About South European Entrepreneurship Engine:

[S3E](#) is an ambitious joint initiative funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe Program. The consortium consists of 4 European partners from the research, innovation and acceleration ecosystem: [HiSeedTech](#) (Portugal), [Institute for Sustainable Development EPLO](#) (Greece), [International Development Ireland](#) (Ireland) and [AUSTRALO](#) (Spain). During the 30-month duration of the project, S3E aims to support 150+ deep tech ventures, including startups, SMEs, academic research teams and technology transfer offices based in Southern Europe.

Follow S3E on [X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) to stay up to date with the project's latest news, and subscribe to the [S3E newsletter](#) for upcoming opportunities for European startups to get involved.

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